

ELF Diacritic Notation - the System Supporting English Pronunciation while Preserving Standard Spelling.

Short Description and User' Guide

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Introduction

ELF Diacritic Notation is a novel diacritic-based system for marking English pronunciation without altering standard orthography. The system preserves full compatibility with standard written English.

The system presented is a simplified reading notation that prioritises intelligibility over phonetic precision and allows for certain exceptions. The goal of the ELF Diacritic Notation is to provide pronunciation guidance sufficient for international communication, taking into account the principles of English as a Lingua Franca (ELF), particularly the Lingua Franca Core (LFC). It is intended primarily for communication among non-native speakers, supporting intelligible reading and clear pronunciation while helping readers avoid automatic first-language habits and guiding them toward appropriate English sound production.

The system is also suitable for learners, as it can present both spelling and pronunciation in a unified “two-in-one” format. This dual-function notation guides articulation while reinforcing spelling patterns, making it a practical tool for self-study materials and pedagogical texts.

ELF Diacritic Notation is described in more detail in the article: *“ELF Diacritic Notation – A Practical System Supporting Intelligible English Pronunciation for Non-native Users while Preserving Standard Spelling”*, available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19007654>.

1. Explanations of Terms Used

The following explanations are provided for clarification the terms used:

- English as a Lingua Franca (ELF) – a contact language among non-native speakers that prioritises intelligibility over adherence to native-speaker norms. The pronunciation features that are crucial for maintaining intelligibility are defined within the Lingua Franca Core (LFC).
- Phoneme – the smallest unit of sound in a language that can change the meaning of a word. Here, it usually refers to the standard dictionary phonemes used for transcribing English pronunciation. The phonetic realisation of a phoneme may vary slightly depending on the context.
- Phonemic transcription – a transcription using IPA symbols to represent phonemes, enclosed in slashes / /. Phonetic transcription, which reflects phonetic variation, is enclosed in square brackets [].
- Diacritic (mark, symbol) – modifying mark added to a letter (e.g., acute ´, macron ¯)
- Character – a letter combined with a diacritic (e.g., ⟨à, é, ï, ð⟩).
- Digraph – a sequence of two letters that represents a phoneme; there are consonant digraphs (⟨sh, th, ph⟩ etc.) and vowel digraphs (e.g., ⟨ai, oo, oa⟩, also ⟨ew, ay⟩).
- Consonants – this term may refer to sounds and phonemes, or to letters or digraphs representing consonants. They are represented as ⟨C⟩ in spelling, /C/ in phonemic transcription,
- Vowels – phonemes that are monophthongs, diphthongs, or triphthongs. Can also refer to letters or digraphs representing vowels. Represented as ⟨V⟩ in spelling, /V/ in phonemic transcription.
- Hiatus – sequence of two vowels belonging to separate syllables.
- Diphthongs – the term used here refers mainly to standard English diphthong phonemes (/eɪ, aɪ, aʊ, oɪ, əʊ|oʊ/), including glide–vowel sequences such as /ju:/.

- Long monophthongs – the term mainly refers to typically long-pronounced monophthongs represented by phonemes (/ɑ:, i:, ɔ:, u:/), regardless of their actual phonetic length.
- Full short vowels (or short vowels) – the phonemes /æ, e, ɒ, ʌ, ʊ, ɪ/. For practical purposes, the category is extended here to include the ‘nurse’ vowel /ɜ: ~ ə/ and the American ‘lot’ vowel /ɑ/.
- Weak vowels – /ʊ, ɪ, i/ in unstressed syllables
- Reduced vowel – schwa /ə/
- Stressed syllable – syllable carrying either primary or secondary stress.
- Stressed vowel – vowel occurring in a primary or secondary stressed syllable.
- Unstressed syllable or vowel – syllable or vowel without primary or secondary stress.
- Closed and open syllables – terms used here in the orthographic sense: an open syllable ends with a vowel letter, while a closed syllable ends with a consonant. Closed syllables within words are often signaled by a consonant cluster or double consonant (e.g., *basket, socket, classic, system*). “-e syllables,” ending with a silent -e (e.g., *-ate, -ure*), are classified as orthographically open.
- Palatalisation – consonant change in which sounds like /t, d, s, z/ turn into /tʃ, dʒ, ʃ, ʒ/; often associated with yod coalescence, i.e., loss of /j/ following a consonant.

2. Short Description of the ELF Diacritic Notation

The diacritic-based notation system is named ELF Diacritic Notation (ELF DN), reflecting its primary design to meet ELF intelligibility requirements. It is intended to provide a default, intelligibility-based pronunciation framework within the limits of the Lingua Franca Core (LFC). It may not capture all subtle phonetic distinctions of native varieties, but it is designed to avoid suggesting pronunciations outside LFC. Skilled users can exceed its guidance, while less proficient users following the basic ELF DN pattern are likely to be understood.

The system limits the use of diacritical marks and avoids applying them where they are not necessary for correctly interpreting pronunciation by a learner who has mastered the basic patterns and rules of English spelling and pronunciation.

2.1. Set of Diacritics

In the ELF Diacritic Notation the following diacritics are used:

For consonants

- acute accent (´) for ⟨ch⟩ pronounced /ʃ/
- macron (¯) for ⟨ch⟩ pronounced /k/ and for ⟨g⟩ before ⟨e, i, y⟩ pronounced /g/

Optional characters, that may be used to indicate exceptions, which are fairly numerous and difficult to memorise.

- The characters ⟨ć, ś⟩ pronounced as /ʃ/
- The characters ⟨ḍ⟩ → /dʒ/; ⟨ṭ⟩ → /tʃ/

For vowels, diacritics are introduced to mark their realisation as diphthongs, long monophthongs, or stressed short vowels.

- acute accent (´) marks diphthongs
- macron (¯) marks long monophthongs
- breve (˘) marks ⟨ö⟩ → /u:/
- grave accent (`) marks other stressed vowels (short), indicating stress regardless of their exact phonemic value

As a supplementary mark, the dieresis may optionally be used to indicate hiatus.

The set of diacritics and characters for the ELF Diacritic Notation is summarized in Table 1.

Table 1.

Diacritical marks in ELF notation with a description of their function and meaning

Description of the Marks	Meaning	Characters Used in Notation
Marks for consonant letters		
Macron (ˉ)	Hard /k, g/	⟨čh⟩→/k/; ⟨ǧ⟩→/g/
Acute accent (´)	“Hushing” /ʃ/	⟨čh⟩ →/ʃ/; (⟨ć, ś⟩ →/ʃ/ optional)
Caron (optional)	Africates	⟨đ⟩ →/dʒ/; ⟨ť⟩ →/tʃ/
Marks for letters-vowels		
Acute accent (´)	Diphthongs /eɪ, aɪ, əʊ, ju:/	⟨á,é⟩→/eɪ/; ⟨í,ý⟩→/aɪ/; ⟨ó⟩→/əʊ oʊ/; ⟨ú⟩→/ju:/
Macron (ˉ)	Long monophthongs /ɑ:, i:, ɔ:, u:/	⟨ā⟩→/ɑ:/; ⟨ē, ī, ŷ⟩→ /i:/; ⟨ō⟩→ /ɔ:/; ⟨ū⟩→ /u:/
Breve (˘ - resembling U)	Long /u:/	⟨ö⟩ → /u:/
Grave accent (`)	Stressed full short vowels /æ, e, ɒ ɑ, ʌ, ɔ, ɪ/ or /ɜ: ɜ:/	⟨à, è, ò, ù, ì, ÿ⟩
Dieresis (¨) (optional)	Unstressed vowel in hiatus: reduced or weak vowel, or hiatic /i/	⟨ä, ë, ö, ü, ï, ÿ⟩

2.2. Marking of Stressed Short Vowels

The grave accent (`) in ELF notation is used to indicate primary or secondary stressed short vowels, including ‘nurse vowels’ /ɜ:|ɜ/. Short stressed vowels are marked in the same way regardless of their precise phonemic value.

Grave accent is omitted in short one- or two-syllable words where stress is predictable:

- Short one-syllable words are typically stressed, so stress-marking grave accents are unnecessary (e.g. *cat*, *jump*). Markings are used to indicate the pronunciation of digraphs (e.g. *hèad*, *frìend*, *còugh*).
- Most two-syllable words are stressed on the first syllable. In these cases, grave accents may be omitted for first-syllable vowels provided the word does not contain a vowel digraph, diphthong, or long monophthong, whose presence could introduce ambiguity or suggest stress on the final syllable. Examples: e.g. *syrup*, *limit*, *happy*, but: *mèadow*, *coùrage*, *còffee*, *bìrdsēed*, *pàtió*.

2.3. Marking of Vowels in Unstressed Syllables

Short vowels in unstressed syllables are not marked regardless of their phonemic value. Vowels in unstressed syllables are marked when they are pronounced as diphthongs or long monophthongs. Occasionally, unstressed digraphs may occur, the pronunciation of which is marked with diacritics.

Unmarked vowels in unstressed syllables are usually pronounced as reduced or weak. Full short vowels are rare in unstressed syllables and their precise pronunciation is generally not crucial for intelligibility.

2.4. Marking of Vowel Digraphs and Sequences

As a general principle, the phonemic value of a digraph is marked by a diacritic applied to one of its letters, following the same rules as for single-letter graphemes. Unstressed digraphs corresponding to schwa or weak /ɪ, i/ remain unmarked. Certain digraphs require special treatment, as detailed in Section 3.2. Special marking rules also apply to vowel–r sequences, which are described in Section 3.3.

2.5. Function Words

High-frequency function words often have atypical pronunciations and are learned as whole words. As a rule, diacritical marks are not used in frequently occurring function words such as:

- articles, prepositions, pronouns, conjunctions, particles, and simple numbers
- auxiliary and modal verbs such as be, have, do, can, may, shall, and will and all their forms (are, would, etc.)

3. Reading ELF Diacritic Notation – User’s Guide

Since the ELF Diacritic Notation does not fully specify pronunciation, reading texts correctly requires not only recognising diacritical marks and characters but also applying typical spelling-to-sound patterns. These patterns are generally acquired naturally during English study; nevertheless, understanding them can help users read both diacritic texts and standard English more accurately.

The following subsections summarize the key rules that a non-native reader should follow when using ELF Diacritic Notation.

3.1. Reading Vowels

In ELF Diacritic Notation, vowels that are long, diphthongs, or stressed short vowels are marked, as these are critical for intelligibility. Clear articulation of marked and stressed vowels is crucial and generally sufficient.

Table 2 shows how vowels are pronounced according to ELF DN marking. The default ELF pronunciation shown is a generally intelligible form to use when the exact pronunciation is unknown to the user. Crucial exceptions are rare and can be memorised - the most important cases are listed below the table.

Table 2.

Vowel pronunciation depending on ELF DN marking (The table does not apply to digraphs and sequences with R)

ELF Diacritic Notation		Pronunciation					Comments
Marking	Examples of Notation	ELF Default	AmE Typical	BrE Typical	Possible Variations	In Exceptions or Rare	
Grave accent (`) (or without diacritic in stressed syllables ¹⁾)	⟨à⟩ or ⟨a⟩ ¹⁾	/æ/				/e/ ^{2a)}	Typically short monophthongs, full, stressed
	⟨è⟩ or ⟨e⟩ ¹⁾	/e/				/ɪ/ ^{2b)}	
	⟨î, ÿ⟩ or ⟨i, y⟩ ¹⁾	/ɪ/					
	⟨ò⟩ or ⟨o⟩ ¹⁾	/ɑ /	/ɒ/	/ʌ/	/ʊ, ɪ/ ^{2c)}		
	⟨ù⟩ or ⟨u⟩ ¹⁾	/ʌ/				/ʊ, ɪ, e/ ^{2d)}	
Without diacritic in unstressed syllables	⟨a⟩	/ə/	/ə/ ³⁾		/ɪ/ ³⁾	/æ/	Typically reduced or weak, not crucial for intelligibility
	⟨e⟩	/ə/	/ə, ɪ/ ³⁾			/e/	
	⟨i, y⟩	/ɪ/	/ɪ, ə, i/ ³⁾				
	⟨o⟩	/ə/	/ə/			/ɑ ɒ/	
	⟨u⟩	/ə/	/ə/ or /jə, jʊ/ ⁴⁾		/ʊ/ ⁵⁾	/ʌ/	
Acute accent (´)	⟨á⟩	/eɪ/					Diphthongs, usually stressed
	⟨é⟩						
	⟨í, ý⟩	/aɪ/					
	⟨ó⟩	/oʊ/	/əʊ/				
	⟨ú⟩	/ju:/			/u:/ ⁵⁾		
Macron (¯)	⟨ā⟩	/ɑ:/			/ɔ:/, /ɒ/ ⁶⁾		Monophthongs, typically long and stressed
	⟨ē⟩	/i:/					
	⟨ī, ŷ⟩						
	⟨ō⟩	/ɔ:/					
	⟨ū⟩	/u:/					
Breve (ˇ)	⟨ö⟩	/u:/					

Notes. (Numbers correspond to references in Table 2.)

1) In ELF Diacritic Notation, stress marking may be omitted where stress is predictable (e.g. in monosyllabic words and many disyllabic words with initial stress). In such cases vowels in stressed syllables should be pronounced as if marked with a grave accent.

- 2) Exceptions for short vowels in stressed syllables:
- a) ⟨a⟩ → /e/: *many, any* (and derivatives such as *anyone*)
 - b) ⟨e⟩ → /ɪ/: *pretty, English*
 - c) ⟨o⟩ → /ʊ/: *woman, wolf, bosom*; ⟨o⟩ → /ɪ/: *women*;
 - d) ⟨u⟩ → /ʊ/: *put, push, pull, full, bull, bush, bullet, bully, cushion, pudding, sugar*;
 ⟨u⟩ → /ɪ/: *busy, business*; ⟨u⟩ → /e/: *bury, burial*
- 3) Unstressed ⟨a, e⟩ may be realized as /ə/ or weak /ɪ/, and ⟨i, y⟩ as /ɪ, ə, i/. These distinctions are not marked because variation in unstressed syllables rarely affects intelligibility.
- 4) Unstressed ⟨u⟩ is pronounced /ə/ in closed syllables and /jə/ or /jʊ/ in open syllables.
- 5) Sequences /ju:, jʊ, jə/ after /d, t, s/ may undergo yod coalescence, e.g. ⟨dú, tú, sú⟩ → /dʒu:, tʃu:, ʃu:/; ⟨du, tu, su⟩ → /dʒʊ, dʒə, tʃʊ, tʃə, ʃʊ, ʃə/ in open unstressed syllables. Pronouncing /ju:, jʊ, jə/ without coalescence remains fully intelligible.
- 6) The spelling ⟨a⟩ is often realised as /ɔ:/ or /ɒ/ after /w/ and before dark /l/. In ELF, it can generally be replaced with /ɑ:/ without risking unintelligibility.
- Examples of words with vowels written in ELF Diacritic Notation are given in Table 5 in Section 4.

3.2 Reading Vowel Sequences (Digraphs and Hiatus)

A sequence of two letters that represents a phoneme is called a digraph; examples of vowel digraphs are e.g., ⟨ai, oo, oa⟩, also ⟨ew, ay⟩. Sequence of two vowels belonging to separate syllables is not a digraph and is called a hiatus.

Vowel digraphs should be in ELF DN typically read according to the letter marked with a diacritic. The unmarked letter should be ignored and not pronounced. E.g: ⟨áú, áí, áy, éa, éi, éy⟩ → /eɪ/, ⟨ēa, ēe, ēi, ēy, ēe⟩ → /i:/ etc.

However, several digraphs can't be marked in the typical way as described above. Such digraphs should be pronounced as shown in table 3. As default ELF pronunciation the American variant is recommended.

Table 3.
Pronunciation of vowel digraphs without marking or with atypical marking

ELF Diacritic Notation		Pronunciation		Remarks
Marking	Examples of Notation	AmE (ELF Default)	BrE	
Without diacritics	⟨ee⟩	/ɪ/		usually stressed, (note: ⟨ēe⟩ → /i:/)
	ending ⟨-ee⟩	/i/		'happy vowel', unstressed
	⟨oo⟩	/ʊ/		usually stressed, (note: ⟨ōo⟩ → /u:/)
	⟨oi, oy⟩	/ɔɪ/		in exceptions of French origin: /ə, wɑ:/
	⟨ew⟩	/ju:/		typical
		/u:/		in sequences: <i>rew, lew, chew, jew</i>
		/oʊ/	/əʊ/	in exception <i>sew</i> and related
⟨au, -eau⟩	/oʊ/	/əʊ/	rare, French origin	
⟨ai, ea, ei, ie, oa, ou, ui, eau⟩	reduced /ə/ or weak /ɪ/		unstressed	
Atypical Marking	⟨òū, òw, āū⟩	/aʊ/		
	⟨àì, ày⟩	/e/		rare, usually stressed

In case of hiatus, the two vowels should be read separately using the rules described in chapter 2.1 and in table 2.

To avoid misinterpretation the dieresis (¨) may be optionally used to indicate separate pronunciation of adjacent vowels. The rule is that the dieresis sign is placed above an unstressed vowel. Examples:

- *fúël, crúël, súèt, rūin, sólóist, prótozóä, créäte, thèâtre*

In sequences ⟨CIV⟩, the dieresis marks hiatic /i/:

- *bàstion, celèstial, pàtió, tiāra, ètiòlogy, cēsium, càlcium, Cèlsius*

The dieresis is not required when both vowels already carry diacritics, as this normally indicates a hiatus; examples:

- *dúèt, cóaguláte, óásis, zòòlogy, cóòperate, ìntúition, cóincidence*

3.3 Reading Vowels Followed by R

In English, the consonant /r/ (or the letter ⟨r⟩) affects the pronunciation of preceding vowels in stressed syllables. Therefore, the rules for reading vowels preceding the letter ⟨r⟩ in ELF DN differ from those described above. The influence of /r/ on vowel pronunciation varies between dialects, but these differences are regular, so a common diacritic notation is used for them.

Sequences involving the letter ⟨r⟩ should be pronounced as shown in table 4. In non-rhotic British English, /r/ shown in brackets is silent when before a consonant or at the end of a word.

As default ELF pronunciation the American variant is recommended.

Table 4.

Pronunciation of vowels followed by R

ELF Diacritic Notation		Pronunciation		Description, Remarks
Marking	Examples of Notation	AmE (ELF Default)	BrE	
Acute accent (´)	⟨ár, -áre, áir, éar, éir⟩	/er/	/eə(r)/	/eɪr/ changes to /er eə(r)/
	⟨ír, ýr⟩	/aɪr/	/aɪə(r)/	/aɪr/ changes to /aɪr aɪə(r)/
	⟨úr, eúr⟩	/jʊr/	/jʊə(r)/	/ju:r/ changes to /jʊr jʊə(r)/*
Macron (¯)	⟨ār⟩	/ɑ:r/	/ɑ:(r)/	
	⟨ōr⟩	/ɔ:r/	/ɔ:(r)	
	⟨ēr, -ēre, ēar, ēer, ēir, īer⟩	/ɪr/	/ɪə(r)/	/i:r/ changes to /ɪr ɪə(r)/
	⟨-ūre, oūr⟩	/ʊr/	/ʊə(r)/	/u:r/ changes to /ʊr ʊə(r)/
	⟨ōūr⟩	/aʊr/	/aʊə(r) /	/au:r/ changes to /aʊr aʊə(r)/
Grave accent (̀) or without diacritic in stressed syllables	⟨àr⟩ or ⟨ar⟩ ²⁾	/er/	/æ(r)/	/æ:r/ changes to /er æ(r)/
	⟨èr, ìr, ÿr, òr, ùr, òur, èur, èar⟩ or ⟨er, ir, yr, or, ur⟩ in stressed syllables	/ɜ/	/ɜ:/	‘Nurse vowel’ before /r/

* Possible yod coalescence, e.g. ⟨dúr⟩→/dʒʊr|dʒʊə(r)/, ⟨túr⟩→/tʃʊr|tʃʊə(r)/, ⟨súr⟩→/ʃʊr|ʃʊə(r)/

Examples of words with vowel digraphs and sequences written using ELF Notation are shown in Table 6 in Section 4.

3.4. Reading Consonants

Consonants marked with diacritics have the pronunciation specified below.

- ⟨g̃⟩ → /g/
- ⟨čh, č̃⟩ → /k/
- ⟨čh, č̃, ś̃⟩ → /ʃ/
- ⟨d̃⟩ → /dʒ/, ⟨t̃⟩ → /tʃ/

In cases where consonants are not marked, pronunciation follows general rules. The following deserve special attention:

- 1) Letter ⟨c⟩ before ⟨e, i, y⟩ is pronounced as /s/, otherwise as /k/. Exceptions almost do not exist.

- 2) Letter ⟨g⟩ before ⟨e, i, y⟩ is usually pronounced as /dʒ/, otherwise as /g/. Exceptions are marked ⟨g̃⟩.
- 3) The digraph ⟨ck⟩ is pronounced as /k/.
- 4) The digraph ⟨ch⟩ is typically pronounced as /tʃ/. Other pronunciations /ʃ/ or /k/ are marked ⟨čh, čh⟩.
- 5) The digraph ⟨sh⟩ is pronounced as /ʃ/.
- 6) The digraph ⟨ph⟩ is pronounced as /f/.
- 7) The digraph ⟨gh⟩ at the beginning of a word or before vowel is typically pronounced as /g/.
- 8) The digraph ⟨gh⟩ before consonant or at the word end is usually mute or pronounced as /f/ in words: *laugh, cough, tough, rough, enough, trough*.
- 9) The digraph ⟨th⟩ is pronounced as /θ/ or /ð/.
- 10) The letter ⟨n⟩ before /g/ or /k/, and the digraph ⟨ng⟩ at the end of a syllable are pronounced as /ŋ/.
- 11) The letter L represents the phoneme /l/ which is pronounced as clear [l] before vowels (e.g., *love* [lʌv]) and as dark [ɫ] elsewhere (e.g., *sālt, fēel* [fi:ɫ]).
- 12) ⟨x⟩ at the beginning of a word is pronounced /z/ (e.g. *xýlophóne*).
- 13) Initial consonants are silent in clusters: *kn-, wr-, gn-, ps-, pn-* (e.g. *knife, knock, wríte, wrong, gnóme, psýchòlogy, pseúdo, pneūmónia*).
- 14) Final consonants are silent in clusters: *-mb, -mn, (lamb, tomb, automn, damn)*.
- 15) ⟨h⟩ is silent in words: *honest, honour, heir, hour* and their derivatives.
- 16) The consonants ⟨s, th, x⟩ are usually voiceless, but in some words and contexts (e.g. when between two vowels) are voiced. Double ⟨ss⟩ is typically voiceless (exc. *dessèrt*).

Palatalisation (/s, z, t, d/ → /ʃ, ʒ, tʃ, dʒ/):

- 17) The sequence ⟨ci⟩ followed by a vowel (⟨ciV⟩) in the same syllable is typically pronounced as /ʃ/. (This does not apply in cases of hiatus, especially in the Latin endings *-cius, -cium, -ciar, -ciary*).
- 18) The sequence ⟨si⟩ followed by a vowel (⟨siV⟩) in the same syllable is typically pronounced as /z/ or /ʃ/, /ʒ/ - if preceded by a vowel, /ʃ/ - if preceded by a consonant or in sequence ⟨ssi⟩. (Not in hiatus, especially in the endings *-sius, -sium*, e.g. *Celsius, magnèsium*).
- 19) The sequence ⟨ti⟩ followed by a vowel (⟨tiV⟩) in the same syllable is typically pronounced as /ʃ/, while ⟨ti⟩ in ⟨stiV⟩ is pronounced as /tʃ/. (Not in hiatus, e.g. *bastion, celèstial, pàtió, tiāra, etiòlogy*, also endings *-tius, -tium, -tiar, -tiary*).
- 20) In the endings ⟨-dure, -ture, -ssure, -sure, -zure⟩ the consonants are pronounced as /dʒ, tʃ, ʃ, ʒ/ e.g.: *prócēdure, náture, prèssure, lèisure, sēizure*.
- 21) In the sequences ⟨du, tu, su⟩ in open syllables the consonants often undergo yod-coalescence and are pronounced as /dʒ, tʃ, ʃ, (ʒ)/ e.g.: *èducáte, státue, situátion, sugar*, (optionally in ELF DN may be marked ⟨ḍ, ṭ, ṣ⟩). Dialect differences occur between BrE and AmE. When the correct pronunciation is uncertain, ELF recommends pronunciation without yod coalescence, which should remain intelligible.
- 22) In exceptional cases (French loanwords) ⟨g, j⟩ are pronounced as /ʒ/: e.g. *prestíge, mirāge, bíjōū*.

In non-rhotic dialect (BrE/RP):

- 23) ‘r’ before consonant is mute in RP.
- 24) -r at the end of a word is mute in RP, unless the next word begins with a vowel, then the final -r is pronounced (the so-called linking r, transcribed in IPA as /-r̩/ e.g. /ka:ˈr̩/).
- 25) -re at the end of a word is pronounced as /ə˞r̩/ (e.g. *thèatre*)

Examples of words with ambiguous or atypical consonant pronunciation written in ELF Notation are shown in Table 8 in Section 4.

3.5. Determining Syllable Stress

Accurate pronunciation of vowels in stressed syllables is key to intelligibility. These vowels should be pronounced correctly and retain their full quality.

In ELF Diacritic Notation, in the vast majority of cases, a diacritic placed over a vowel (except dieresis) indicates the stressed syllable. Therefore, vowels marked with such diacritics should be pronounced clearly and without reduction. However, a diacritic does not always indicate stress. Diacritics may also be omitted in one- and two-syllable words.

Stress can be determined more precisely by combining diacritic interpretation with general stress rules:

- Grave accent (`) – directly indicates a stressed vowel.
- Macron or breve (¯ / ˇ) – long monophthongs are almost always stressed, with rare exceptions occurring particularly in final syllables.
- Acute accent (´) – diphthongs are usually stressed, but may be unstressed particularly in the final syllable.
- Vowel digraphs ⟨oo, ee, ew, oi, oy⟩ (without diacritics) representing phonemes /oʊ, ɪ, ju:, u:, ɔɪ/ are usually stressed.
- Adjacent syllables rarely both carry stress – if neighboring syllables have diacritics, the diphthong or long monophthong may remain unstressed (e.g., *rheūmàtic*).
- Two-syllable words without diacritics – stress is assumed on the first syllable.
- Long, multi-syllable, or compound words – primary and secondary stress often occur. Primary stress is often on the second element (e.g., *èlemèntary*), but in compounds of two words it usually falls on the first element (*blàckbōard, grēenhòuse, newspáper, schöoltēacher, týpewriter*).

5. Examples of Using ELF Diacritic Notation

Tables 5–7 present examples of words written in ELF Diacritic Notation with explanatory notes. Table 5 illustrates vowel marking and pronunciation, Table 6 vowel digraphs, and Table 7 consonant marking. The lists cover a wide range of spelling–pronunciation combinations, including irregular and rare cases, demonstrating the effectiveness of the system.

Table 5.

Examples of Words with Vowels and Vowel-r Sequences in ELF Notation

	Diacritic Notation	Examples Written Using ELF Diacritic Notation	BrE/AmE pronounc.	Default ELF Pron., Remarks
acute accent (´) - diphthongs	á	náme, creátor, vácátion	/eɪ/	
	ár, -áre	párent, sháring, cáre	/eə(r) er/	/er/
	é	bàllét, úkuléle, càfé, étúde	/eɪ/	rare
	ó	ópen, sófa	/əʊ oʊ/	/oʊ/
	ú	úse, únit, músic, valúe	/ju:/	
	úr, -úre	fúry, cúrious, Éurope, cúre, endúre	jʊə(r), jʊr/	/jʊr /
	í	fíne, clímb, líe, supplíer, sciénce	/aɪ/	
	ý	ský, replý, dený, supplý		
	-íre, -ýre	fíre, týre	/aɪə(r) aɪr/	/aɪr/
	írV, ýrV	pírate, írony, pýrománia, fíring		

	Diacritic Notation	Examples Written Using ELF Diacritic Notation	BrE/AmE pronounc.	Default ELF Pron./Remarks	
Macron (¯) - full long monophthongs	ā	fāther, cār, āria, wāter, cāl, whāt, wās, wānt, wāsh, sālt, ālter	/ɑ:/ (/ɔ:/, /ɒ/)	/ɑ:/	
	ē	prócēdure, thēater	/i:/		
	ēr, -ēre	hēró, pēriod, sincēre	/ɪə(r) ɪr/	/ ɪr/	
	ī, ŷ	machīne, mosquító	/i:/		
	ō	mōre, bōrn	/ɔ:/		
	ū	rūle, Jūne	/u:/		
	-ūre	lūre, assūre	/ʊə(r) ʊr/	/ʊr /	
Breve (˘)	ö, ȳ	möve, pröve, löse	/u:/		
Grave accent (`) or not marked in stressed syllable	à, a	fà mily, cat, accent, massive,	/æ/		
		many, any	/e/	exceptions	
	àr, a àrr, arr	càravan, màrathon, harass,	/ æ(r) er/	/er/	
		arrów, carry			
	è, e	cèlebráte, bed, lemon, extra, wedding	/e/		
	ò, o	mònastery hot, profit, monster	/ɒ ɑ/	/ɑ/	
		love, come, son	/ʌ/		
		wolf, woman / women	/ʊ/, /ɪ/	exceptions	
	ù, u	sun, jump,	/ʌ/		
		pùsh-button, pùllóver, pull	/ʊ/	exceptions	
		bùsiness, busy	/ɪ/	exceptions	
	ì, i ỳ, y	big, milk, simple, limit, visibilità, amphìbia, ambìvalent systèmeàtic, sýllable, system, myth	strong /ɪ/		
èr, (er stress.) ìr, (ir) ỳr, (yr) òr, (or) ùr, (ur)		pèrmanent, therm vìrtual, bìrdwātcher, bìrd myrrh, myrtle, mỳrmecòlogy word fùrniture, fur, nurse	/ɜ: ɜ/	/ɜ/ only in R-closed stressed syllables	
Not marked in unstressed syllable	a	banàna, dàta, dollar, paràde	/ə/,	/ə/	
		amphìbia, ambìvalent	(exc./æ/)		
		còurage, pàlace	weak /ɪ/		
	e	cèlebráte, òpera, tèacher	/ə/,	/ə/	
		bènefit	/ɪ/weak		
		áthēist, créate, reènter,	/i/		
	o	lemon, májor, doctor, gallon	/ə/	/ə/	
	u	in closed syllable	syrup, circus, sulfur, succèss	/ə/	/ə/
		in open syllable	dòcument, règular, rèfugēe, àctual, èducáte, figure, minute	/jə, jʊ, ə, (ɪ) /	/jə, jʊ/
	i	àctivity, taxi, bikìni (happy v.) tīāra, mediēval (hiatuses)	/i/	/ɪ/	
		limit, mèdicine,	/ɪ/weak		
		fà mily, orìginal pòssible, hòrrible, àctivity, visibilità, pòsitive, pencil, fossil, civil	/ə/		
y	happy, fà mily, (happy v.)	/i/	/ɪ/		
	mythòlogy pòlysylàbic,	/ɪ/weak			
	anàlysis, satyr, martyr	/ə/,			

Table 6.

Examples of Vowel Digraphs and Their R-Extended Sequences in ELF Notation

Sequences pronounced as Vowels or Diphtongs					Hiatuses and Exceptions
Notation		BrE/AmE Pronounc.	Comments	Examples	
ai	ái	/eɪ/	stressed or unstressed	detáil(v), main, ráinbàrrel dētáil(n), máintáin, dáy, anywáy,	
	áír	/eə(r) er/		fair, aircraft, áirbōarder	
	àì ày	/e/	atypical marking	sàid, agàin (or agáin), plàid, sàys	
	-ain	/-ən, -ɪn/	non-str. endings -ain	certain, curtain, captain, mòuntain,	
ea	ēa	/i:/	dominant pron. ~60%	ēat, sēa, tēacher	hiat.: reality, reàct rēarm créate thēâtre, idēā, àrēā
	ēar	/ɪə(r) ɪr/	breaking before /r/ (BrE)	clēar, wēary	
	eār	/ɑ:/		heārt	
	éa	/eɪ/		gréat, bréak	
	éar	/eə(r) er/		béar, swéar	
	èa	/e/		hèad, brèad, mèadow	
	èar	/ɜ:/	R-closed str. syl.	pèarl, lèarn, èarnestly	
	ea	/ə/		ócean, sergeant	
ee	ēe	/i:/	dominant pron.	slēep, quēen, birdsēed	hiat.: reènter
	ēer	/ɪə(r) ɪr/	breaking before /r/ (BrE)	enginēer, chēery, bēer	
	ee	/ɪ/	rare, no diacritic	breeches, been,	
	-ee	/i/	unstr. ending, happy vowel	coffee, committee	
ei ey	éi éy	/eɪ/	dominant pron.	wéight gréy, whéy,	hiat.: rēinstāl áthēist déity
	ēi ēy	/i:/		recēive, cēiling kēy, gēyser	
	ēir	/ɪə(r) ɪr/	exceptions	wēird	
	éir	/eə(r) er/	exceptions	héir, théir	
	eý	/aɪ/		eýe, geýser (US)	
	-ey	/i/	unstr. happy vowel,	money	
	èi	/e/	rare	lèisure, hèifer,	
	ei	/ɪ, ə/	unstressed, weak or reduced	foreign, forfeit	
ie	īe	/i:/	dom. pron. > 50%	fīeld, belīeve, thīef	hiat.: mediēval clīent quīet
	íe, ýe	/aɪ/		líe, fríed, rýe	
	ìe	/ɪ/	rare	sìeve	
	īer	/ɪə(r) ɪr/	rare	pīerce, tīer, bīer, fierce	
	ìè	/e/	only exceptions	friènd	
	ie	/ɪ, ə/	unstressed, weak or reduced	ancient, kerchief	
	-ie(d/s)	/i/	ending, happy vowel	mōvie, cookie(s), carried	
oa	óa	/əʊ oʊ/	dominant pron.	bóat, cóat, róad	hiat.: óásis cóaguláte prótozóa
	ōa	/ɔ:/	rare	bōard, brōad	
	oa	/ə/	unstressed, reduced	cùpboard	
oe	óe	/əʊ oʊ/	dominant	tóe	exc. does, phoēnix
	öe	/u:/		shöe(s)	

Sequences pronounced as Vowels or Diphtongs				Hiatuses and Exceptions	
Notation	Pronounc.	Comments	Examples		
oi	oi oy	/ɔɪ/	stressed or unstressed no diacritic	choice, boil, voice boy, cònvoy, royal,	hiat.: <i>còincidence</i> <i>sólóist</i> , <i>chóir</i>
	oi	/ə/ /wa:/,	exceptions, French origin no diacritic	tórtois, cònnaisseur, mèmoire	
oo	öo	/u:/	dominant pron. ~60%	möon, föod, kàngaröö	hiat.: <i>zòology</i> , <i>còöperate</i>
	oo	/ʊ/	~30%, no diacritic	book, look, foot	
	ōo	/ɔ:/		dōor, flōor, mōor	
	òo	/ʌ/ (~ p a/)	exceptions	blòod, flòod	
	óo	/əʊ oʊ/	exceptions	bróoch	
ou ow	óu ów	/əʊ oʊ/		álthóugh snów, lów	exc. /p a/ - <i>knòwledge</i>
	oū	/u:/		througħ	
	oūr	/ʊə(r) ʊr/		toūrist, coūrier	
	òu	/p a/		còugh	
	où	/ʌ/		yoùng, coùple, toùgh	
	òw	/aʊ/	atypical marking	cròwn, flòwer	
	ōū			abòūt, pròūd,	
	òūr	/aʊə(r) aʊr/		flòūr, hòūrly	
	ōu	/ɔ:/		thòught,	
	ōur	/ɔ:(r)/		fòur	
	òur	/ɜ:/	R-closed str. syl. (rare)	jòurney	
	ou	/ə/	non-str. endings -ous, -our	fámous, colour	
au aw	āw āu	/ɔ:~ ɒ ~ ɑ:/	pron. depending on dialect Intelligible default ELF: /ɑ:/	drāw, crāwl, fāult, tāught, sāuce,	
	āu or àu	/ɑ:/ or /æ/		āunt, lāugh àunt, làugh	
	áu,	/eɪ/	exceptions	gáuge	
	āū,	/aʊ/	atypical marking	sāuerkrāūt,	
	au	/oʊ əʊ/	no diacritic , exception	gauche	
ue	-úe, úe	/ju:/		válúe, ārgúe, Túesday	hiat.: <i>fúël</i> , <i>dùèt</i> <i>crüël</i> , <i>süèt</i>
	-ūe	/u:/		blūe	
	ué	/weɪ/	rare	suéde	
ui	úi	/ju:/		súit	hiat.: <i>rūin</i> , <i>ìntuìtion</i> exc. /gwɪ/- <i>pènguin</i> , <i>ànguish</i>
	ūi	/u:/		frūit, crūise	
	uí, uý	/aɪ/		guíde, buý	
	uì	/ɪ/ strong		buìld, guìlty,	
	ui	weak /ɪ/	unstressed	guitār, cìrcuit, bìscuit	
eu	eū	/u:/	rare	rheūmàtic, sleūth	hiat.: <i>reúse</i> <i>músēum</i> exc.: /ɜ:/ - <i>massèuse</i> /ɔɪ/ - <i>Freud</i>
	eú	/ju:/	typical initial eu- /ju:/	eúphoric, feúd	
	eúr	/jʊə(r) jʊr/		Eúrope	
	-èur	/ɜ:/	in stress. endings -èur	cònnaisseur, massèur	
	-eur	/ə/	in non-str. endings -eur	àmateur	
ew	ew	/ju:/	typical, no diacritic	few, ewe, steward	
	ew	/u:/	after ⟨ch, j, l, r⟩	crew, jewel, chew, lewd	
	ew	/əʊ oʊ/	exceptions	sew, sewing	
eau	eaú	/ju:/	French origin	beaúty	
	eāu	/p a/		búreāucracy	
	-eau	/əʊ oʊ/	no diacritic , French origin	beau, búreau, plateau	
	eau	/ə/		búreaucrat	

Table 7.*Examples of Words with Ambiguous or Atypical Consonant Pronunciation in ELF Notation*

Notation	Pron. IPA	Typical Context, Notes,	Examples Written Using ELF Diacritic Notation (Some examples also in IPA notation)
g	/g/	typical, except below	gráve, good
	/dʒ/	typical before e, i, y	gentle, ginger, coūrage, Ēgypt
ġ	/g/	irregular before e, i, y mainly Germanic, Greek origin	ġirl, ġive, ġift, ġeese, tġger, ġecko, ġeyser, ġġgabyte, ġynecology
gh	/g/	typical before vowel	ghóst, ghāstly, gherkin, ghetto, spaghètti
	mute	before consonant or at the end	thóugh, dóugh, ālthóugh, thóught, slāughter (exc. <i>Baghdad</i>)
	/f/	exceptions	lāugh, lāughter, coūgh, tōugh
c	/k/	typical, except below	cat, coffee, cōre, clóse, lecture, (exc.: <i>caesúra, caesium/cēsium, facāde/façāde</i>)
	/s/	before e, i, y	cēiling, circus. cíder, cġan, (exc.: <i>sceptic/skeptíc, Celtic /'keltɪk, 'seltɪk/</i>)
	/ʃ/	exceptions, optional ⟨ć⟩	ócean
ck	/k/	typical	back, socket
ch	/tʃ/	typical	chief, much, cherry
	/k/	scientific, Greek origin	sġhool, ġhēmistry, ġháos, ārchitect
	/ʃ/	French origin, borrowings	ġhef, maġhine, bróchure
ci	/ʃ/	seq. ⟨ciV⟩: endings -cial, -cian - cious, -cient	special, sócial, rácial, spácious, grácious, ancient, physician
	/si/	in hiatus (optionally marked by dieresis)	pronunciátion, annūnciáte, calciūm
s	/s/	typical, except below	snów, some
	/z/,	usually between vowels (not double ss)	ēasy, busy, excúse(v), (but <i>massive, fossil, lesson</i> except <i>dessèrt</i>)
	/ʒ, ʒ/	endings -ssure, -sure, other rare, optionally marked ⟨ś⟩	prèssure, lèisure, mèasure, clósure śugar, śure
si	/ʃ/	endings: -Csion, -ssion, -ssia(n)	version, pension, passion, Russia(n),
	/z/	endings: -Vsion, -Vsia(n)	vision, fúision, decision, Ásian
	/si, zi/	in hiatus, optionally marked by (¨)	endings -sius, -sium: Celsiūm, cēsium
d	/d/	typical	duck
	/dʒ/	endings -dure, and exceptions optionally marked by caron ⟨ď⟩	prócēdure, soldġier, èďucáte
	/d, dj, dʒ/	before u in open syl. ⟨du, dū, dú⟩ pronounc. depends on the dialect	dūal, dúne, dūring
t	/t/	typical	task
	/tʃ/	endings -ture, and some exceptions optionally marked by caron ⟨ť⟩	fűrniture, náture, lecture àċtűal, riťűal
	/t, tj, tʃ/	before u in open syl. ⟨tu, tū, tú⟩ pronounc. depends on the dialect	Tűesdáy, tűtor
ti	/tʃ/	seq. ⟨stiV⟩: e.g., -stion, -stian	question, Christian,
	/ʃ/	seq. ⟨tiV⟩: endings e.g., -tion, -tial, -tious, -tient, -tian, -tia, -tiáte, -tiátion, -tiáble, and other	nátion, action, spátial, pártial, initial, ostentátious, pátient, Egyptian, militia, inítiáte, negótiátion, negótiáble, rátió
	/ti-/	hiatuses, (optionally marked by dieresis),	bàstion, celèstial, tiāra, etiòlogy, stròntium, pàtió
th	/θ/	typical, except below	myth, think, thumb
	/ð/	usually between vowels	mother, fāther, bother (but <i>ēther, āuthor, method</i>)

Notation	Pron. IPA	Typical Context, Notes,	Examples Written Using ELF Diacritic Notation
x	/ks/	typical, except below	box, wax, expànd
	/kʃ/	bef. u in op. syl., endings, -xure, -xury, -xual, -xious, -xion, -xiety	lùxury /'lʌkʃəri/, sèxual, anxious, complèxion
	/gz/	prefix ex- before vowel	exàmine, èxecúte, exhāust
	/z/	at the word beginning	xýlophóne, xenon, xènophóbia
qu	/kw/	typical	quíèt, liquid
	/k/	endings -que, borrowings	únique, conquer, mosquító
ng	/ŋ/	in endings or before cons.	ring, long
	/ŋg/	if before vowel	longer
nk, nx	/ŋk/		bank, link, anxious
g, j, z	/ʒ/	exceptions, French origin	prestīge, mirāge, bijouū àzure, sēizure
cz	/tʃ/	exceptions	Czech, czardaś,
	/z/		czar

5. Summary – Example of Use

In order to demonstrate the use of ELF Diacritic Notation in practice, this summary is marked with diacritics according to the rules described.

The key feature of presented diacritic-based method for recording pronunciation is that, after removing the diacritics, the notation aligns with standard spelling. The ELF Diacritic Notation achieves accuracy that is usually sufficient for intelligibility in international communication according to the principles of the Lingua Franca Core (LFC). Thanks to diacritics, the system represents pronunciation almost as predictably as more regular alphabetic orthographies, making it intuitive for readers familiar with standard spelling conventions.

ELF Diacritic Notation is primarily intended for use between non-native speakers, supporting intelligible reading in contexts such as international business or technical meetings. The author's practical experience suggests that, particularly through the explicit marking of stress and vowel quality, the use of ELF DN can help disrupt automatic pronunciation habits that learners transfer from their first language, helping them read English more consciously and clearly. This is especially important in formal oral presentations.

The system is also potentially useful in English language teaching, helping students master both spelling and pronunciation through a unified "two-in-one" notation suitable for didactic texts. It is particularly beneficial for independent learners who rely more on visual memory, though it also supports correct articulation for other students. The notation system can be extended with additional diacritic marks and characters to represent pronunciation with greater precision.

The proposed system is not the only possible approach to addressing this issue and may be further refined. Feedback from teachers, learners, and other researchers is welcomed, as this work is intended as a foundation for further research. The system could serve as a practical framework for simplified, globally intelligible pronunciation in English as a Lingua Franca. Future work may explore applications of ELF DN in ELF pedagogy, English language teaching, and independent learning contexts.